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SCREENING OF BIOACTIVE EFFICIENCY ON *CALOTROPIS GIGANTEA* (LINN) R. BR LEAVES AND STEMS.

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ABSTRACT

Calotropis gigantea is a milkweed, gigantic Swallow wort. *Calotropis* species is a common wasteland weed and are widely used as alternative therapeutic tool for the prevention or treatment of many diseases. This study was designed to extract n- heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and aqueous extracts from leaves and stems by Soxhlet method. To screen the presence of the bioactive compounds, was identified by phytochemical screening assays. To evaluate total antioxidant activity by various radical scavenging assays and to investigate the antimicrobial assays and bioassays such as mosquitocidal activity, antibiofilm activity, antiangiogenic assay and cytotoxicity – MTT Assay were performed. This study showed presence of various phytochemicals and the extracts were significantly showed more effective free radical scavenging activity. Out of all the extracts, ethyl acetate extracts of leaves and stems showed good efficiency in antimicrobial activity, mosquitocidal activity, antibiofilm activity, antiangiogenic assay and cytotoxicity assay showed potentially high values on ethyl acetate extract of leaves and stems. From the observed results *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br leaves and stems can be used as potentially active for various clinical purposes.

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INTRODUCTION

Plant derived medicines are about 80% of the world population, mainly in the developing countries, for primary health care because of better cultural acceptability, better compatibility with human body and fewer side effects. The quest for plants with antimicrobial properties continue to receive attention due to development of multiple drug resistance, an increased awareness of the limited ability of synthetic pharmaceutical products to control major diseases and adverse effects of synthetic products on host such as hypersensitivity, immunosuppression and allergic reactions. The relatively lower incidence of adverse reaction to the plant preparations compared to modern conventional pharmaceuticals, coupled with their reduced cost, is also encouraging both the consuming public and national health care institutions to consider plant medicines as alternative to synthetic drugs. These are mostly the secondary metabolites. Plant based antimicrobial represents a vast untapped source of medicines and needed to be explored further. They have enormous therapeutic potential and are effective in treatment of infectious disease. In this context, "Medicinal plants are rightly said to be Tradition of yesterday and drugs of tomorrow" (1).

The milkweed family (Asclepiadaceae) comprises some 200 genera and 2500 species of perennial shrubs and herbs distributed through the tropics and temperate areas of the world (2). *Calotropis* species are non-cultivated, xerophytic shrubs of geographic distribution covering Asia, Africa and northeast of South America. In India two species viz, *Calotropis procera* and *Calotropis gigantea* are widely distributed. *Calotropis gigantea* R.Br. (Asclepiadaceae), commonly known as milk weed or swallow-wort, is a medicinal plant widely used as a folk medicine in India as a rich source of biologically active compounds capable of promoting diverse benefits such as control for dermal fungal infections, antimicrobial and pain relief among other useful properties (3,4).

Calotropis gigantea commonly known as Milk-Weed or Swallow wart is widely used medicinal plant in Indian subcontinent (5, 6). It has long ethanobotanical history and extensive uses in traditional medicine. This grows abundantly in India, Malaysia, and Philippines etc. *Calotropis gigantea* belongs to the family Asclepiadaceae. It is a small shrub growing 4 m tall it has clusters of waxy flowers that are either white or lavender in colour, the plant has oval green leaves on milky stem, having cardio toxic, emetocarthartic and digitalic properties the plant is very effective in treating leprosy, elephantiasis, chronic rheumatism, ulcer and skin diseases. *Calotropis gigantea* (*C. gigantea*), a common medicinal plant in Indian subcontinent, has purgative, anthelmintic, anti-convulsant, sedative and anti-pyretic effect (7, 8). Several phytoconstituents have been isolated and identified from different parts of the *C. gigantea* belonging to the category of sterols and triterpenoids (9).

A literature review showed that *Calotropis Gigantea* contained cardenolide, glycosides, a non-protein, amino acid, flavonoids and steroids. *Calotropis gigantea* in small dose are also useful in the treatment of cold, cough, asthma inflammatory diseases and loss of digestive and analgesic property of *C. Gigantea*. (10, 11) Milky sap is used in the treatment of boils, scabies, burns, bruises, cuts, sores, stopping blood, and wound healing; Leaves are used in chest congestion and cardiovascular conditions. The roots and barks of *C. gigantea* are in use for paralysis, fits, epilepsy, and convulsions in children. Shoot, leaf, roots flowers and latex extracts are reported to have antibacterial and antifungal properties by researchers. (12) In the present study, *C. gigantea* leaves and stems extracts in different organic solvents were screened especially for the presence of terpenoids and steroids bioactive phytochemical compounds. The main objective of the present study is to investigate comparative efficacy of leaves and stems of *C. gigantea* and identified the specific target terpenoids and steroids bioactive phytochemical compounds from ethyl acetate extracts of *C. gigantea* leaves and stems.

Study area:

Azhagar hills of Eastern Ghats is lying approximately between 77°30 and 78°20 longitude and 10°05' – 10°09' latitude. The elevation of the area of investigation ranges from 650 to 3000 feet above sea level. Variations in the altitude and rainfall have a bearing on the vegetation in general. The floristic divisions of the area of investigation consist of deciduous thorny scrub forest, dry deciduous forest, and evergreen moist mixed deciduous forest and savannah grasslands.

Distribution:

Throughout India, Ceylon-Malay Island, S. China. (13)

Botanical Description:

A tall shrub reaching 2.4-3m high; yellowish white, furrowed; branches stout, terete, more or less covered (especially the younger ones) with fine appressed cottony pubescence. Leaves 1-20 by 3.8-10 cm, sessile or nearly so, elliptic-oblong or obovate-oblong, acute, thick, glaucous-green, clothed beneath and more or less above with fine cottony tomentum; base narrow, cordate. Flowers inodorous, purplish or white. Calyx divided to the base; sepals 6 by 4 mm, ovate, acute, cottony. Corolla 2cm long or more; lobes 1.3-1.6cm long, deltoid-ovate, subacute, revolute and twisted in age; lobes of the corona 1.3cm. Long by 5mm. pubescent on the slightly thickened margin, the apex rounded with 2 obtuse auricles just below it. Follicles 9-10 cm. Long, broad, thick, fleshy, ventricose, green. Seeds numerous, 6 by 5 mm. broadly ovate, flattened narrowly margined, minutely tomentose, brown coma 2.5-3.2 cm long.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Chemicals and Solvents:

2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH), Ascorbic acid, Glass Petri plates, plastic 96 well titration plates, Agar, Peptone, NaCl, Yeast, Distilled water, Tetramycin (Sigma and Himedia). Organic solvents - n-heptane, ethylacetate, ethanol, methanol and DMSO. Sodium nitroprusside, Phosphate buffer, Griess reagent, Distilled deionized water, PBS, H₂SO₄, Dragendroff's reagent,

Mayer's reagent, Wagner's reagent, Hager's reagent, Fehling's solution A and B, sodium picrate, FeCl₃, ninhydrin, sodium chloride, copper sulphate, HNO₃, Molisch's reagent, lead sub acetate, dilute ammonia solution, aluminum chloride, NaOH, HCL, chloroform, acetic anhydride, Griess reagent, nitroblue tetrazolium, DMSO, Sodium nitroprusside in phosphate buffer, deoxyribose, EDTA, H₂O₂, ascorbate, KH₂PO₄-KOH buffer, TBA, Luria Bertane agar plates, Fertile white Leghorn chicken eggs, sterile forceps, cellophane tape, filter paper discs, "O"-type brush, sterile blade, 26- gauze needle, 18×13×4-cm enamel trays, pedigree dog biscuits and yeast. All the chemicals and solvents used were of the highest purity and analytical grade.

Collection of plant material:

Calotropis gigantea (white flower) plant parts were collected from different locations of Azhagar Hill (Eastern Ghats), Madurai, Tamilnadu, South India during the year 2015–2016. Plant specimens were photographed and collected on the spot (Azhagar Hill area), pressed, dried (in herbarium sheet) authenticated in Rapinat Herbarium as "MVS OO14 *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R. Br" shown in plate 1.

Botanical name: *Calotropis gigantea* (L.) R.Br

Taxonomic classification:

Kingdom: Plantae – Plants

Phylum: Tracheophyta– Vascular plants

Subphylum: Euphyllophytina– Seed plants

Class: Magnoliopsida – Flowering plants

Subclass: Asteridae – Dicotyledons

Order: Gentianales

Family: Apocynaceae – Milkweed family

Subfamily: Asclepiadoideae

Genus: *Calotropis* – calotropis

Species: *gigantea* (L.) R.Br

Plate:1 *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R. Br Plant

Plate 1 *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R. Br Plant, Taxonomic classification and photograph of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R. Br (white flowers).

Preparation of extracts:

The freshly collected plant materials (leaves and stem) were washed thoroughly in tap water, shade dried at room temperature (°C). After drying for 2 to 3 weeks, the dried plant parts (leaves and stem) were ground in an electric pulverizer to get the powder. 10 g of the powdered plant parts (leaves and stem) was weighed using an electronic balance, and used for solvent extraction. The plant samples were successively extracted with n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and distilled water using soxhlet apparatus and the air dried and the residue thus obtained was stored in tightly closed glass vials in the refrigerator (-20°C) for further use.(14,15)

Preliminary phytochemical screening

Preliminary phytochemical analysis was performed for establishing the phyto-constituents (alkaloids, tannins, glycosides, steroids and terpenoids) present in the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and aqueous extracts. Chemical tests for the screening and identification of bioactive chemical constituents in the medicinal plants under study were carried out in extracts using the standard procedures as described by Sofowara (1993), Trease and Evans (1989), (2002) and Harborne (1973). Identification tests for the various chemicals were carried out to test the presence of various chemical constituents.

Phytochemical analysis:

The n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts (1 g) was completely dissolved in 100 mL of its own mother solvents. It was prepared as the stock solution. The obtained stock solution was used for phytochemical screening following the methodology.

Methods of Qualitative phytochemical analysis

The leaf extracts were tested for the presence of bioactive compounds by using following standard methods (16-18).

1. Test for alkaloids:

Methanolic extract was warmed with 2% H₂SO₄ for two minutes .it is filtered and few drops of reagents were added and indicated the presence of alkaloids.

a. Dragendroff's test:

To 5 ml of extract few drops of Dragendroff's reagent was added for the formation of orange coloured precipitate. An orange precipitation indicates the positive.

b. Mayer's test:

To 5 ml of extract few drops of Mayer's reagent was added for the formation of creamy-white coloured precipitate. This precipitation indicates positive.

c. Wagner's test:

To 5 ml of extract few drops of Wagner's reagent was added for the formation of Reddish brown coloured precipitate. This reddish brown coloured precipitation indicates positive.

d. Hager's test:

To 3 ml of extract few drops of Hager's reagent (Picric Acid (1%) - was added for the formation of prominent yellow colored precipitate. This yellow colored precipitation is positive.

2. Test for Glycosides:

5ml of diluted sulphuric acid was added in extracts in a test tube and boiled for fifteen minutes in a water bath. It was then cooled and neutralized with 20% potassium hydroxides solution. A mixture of 10ml of equal parts of Fehling's solution A and B were added and boiled for five minutes. A more dense red precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides

a. Baljet's Test:

To 5 mL of the extract few drops of sodium picrate was added to observe yellow to orange colour.

b. Keller-Killiani test:

To 5 mL of the extract few drops of ferric chloride solution was added and mixed, then sulphuric acid containing ferric chloride solution was added, it forms two layers showing reddish brown while upper layer turns bluish green indicates the presence of glycosides

3. Test for proteins:**a. Ninhydrin test:**

To the test solution added 1 ml of 0.2 % ninhydrin solution, violet color indicates the presence of protein in sample

b. Biuret test:

To 3 mL of the extract few drops of 10% sodium chloride and 1% copper sulphate was added for the formation of violet or purple color. On addition of alkali, it becomes dark violet.

c. Xanthoprotein test:

To 3 mL of the extract few drops of HNO₃ reagent was added for the formation of intensely yellow colour.

4. Test for carbohydrates:**a. Molisch's test:**

To a small amount of the extract few drops of Molisch's reagent was added followed by the addition of conc. H₂SO₄ along the sides of the test tube. The mixture was then allowed to stand for 2 min and then diluted with 5 mL of distilled water. Formation of red or dull violet colour at the interface of two layers indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

b. Fehling's test:

The extract was treated with 5 ml of Fehling's solution (A and B) and kept in boiling water bath. The formation of yellow or red color precipitate indicates the presence of reducing sugar

5. Test for Tannins:

A small quantity of extract is boiled with 5 ml of 45% solution ethanol for 5 minutes. Each of the mixture is cooled and filtered. Filtrate was used to the following test.

a. Lead Sub Acetate:

Test 1ml of the different filtrate was added with three drops of lead sub acetate solution. A cream gelatinous precipitation indicates positive test for Tannins.

b. Ferric Chloride Test:

1ml each of filtrate is diluted with distilled water and added with two drops of ferric chloride. A transient greenish to black color indicates the presence of Tannins.

6. Test for saponins:**a. Foam test:**

To a small amount of the extract few drops of distilled water was added and shaken vigorously until persistent foam was observed.

7. Test for Flavonoids:

A small quantity of extracts is heated with 10ml of ethyl acetate in boiling water for 3 minutes. The mixture is filtered differently and the filtrates are used for the following test

a. Ammonium Test:

The filtrate was shaken with 1 ml of dilute ammonia solution (1%). The layers were allowed to separate. A yellow coloration was observed at ammonium layer. This indicates the presence of flavonoids.

b. Aluminium Chloride Test:

The filtrates were shaken with 1 ml of 1% aluminum chloride solution and observed for light yellow color .it indicated the presence of Flavonoids and diluted NaOH and HCL was added .A yellow solution that turns colorless indicates positive.

8. Test for sterols:**a. Liebermann-Burchard test:**

To a small amount of the extract few drops of chloroform, acetic anhydride and H₂SO₄ was added along the sides of the test tube to observe the formation of dark red or pink colour.

9. Test for Terpenoids:**a. Salkowski Test:**

The extract was mixed with 2ml of chloroform and concentrate H₂SO₄ (3ml) is carefully added to form a layer. A reddish brown coloration of the interface is formed to show positive result of presence of terpenoids.

Identification Tests

The tests were done to find the presence of the active chemical constituents such as steroids and terpenoids by the following procedure are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Phytochemical investigation of *C. gigantea* (L.) R. Br leaves and stem on TLC plate.

Phytochemicals identification tests			
Phytochemical Compounds	Spraying reagent for TLC	Observation	References
Terpenoids and Steroids	5ml acetic anhydride + 5ml conc.H ₂ SO ₄ at 40°C mixture (Liebermann-Burchard reagent)	Pink or red colouration – Terpenoids Violet to blue - Steroids	Harborne, 1973 &1984, Kumar et,al 2007

In vitro* antioxidant assays*Free radical scavenging effects of the leaves and stems of *C.gigantea***

The leaves and stems extracts were tested for their scavenging activity against the stable free radical DPPH (2, 2'-diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl). The ability of the leaves and stems extracts to scavenge DPPH was studied in a dot plot rapid screening assay (Dot plot method) and quantified using a spectrophotometric assay (Photometric method) and SO, NO, OH radical-scavenging activity as proposed by Soler-Rivas *et al* (2000), Abdelaaty *et al* (2012) and Mensor *et al* (2001) respectively.

DPPH radical-scavenging activity (Abdelaaty *et al.*, 2012)**Dot plot Method:****Rapid screening of antioxidant activity by dot plot assay:**

Aliquots (3µl) of *C.gigantea* extracts were spotted on a TLC plate (Merck Silica gel F254 plates) and allowed to dry for a few minutes. The TLC plate bearing the dry spots was placed upside down for 10 seconds in the solution of DPPH. The spots exhibiting radical scavenging, antioxidant activity showed up as yellow spots in a violet background. The intensity of the yellow colour depends on the amount and nature of the radical scavenger present in the spot. When DPPH reacts with a hydrogen donor, the reduced (molecular) form (DPPH) is generated, accompanied by the disappearance of the violet colour. (16, 19). This assay was used to establish whether different extracts of *Calotropis gigantea* (L.) R. Br leaves and stem (n-heptane, ethylacetate, ethanol and aqueous) had radical scavenging activity.

DPPH Photometric method:

The antioxidant activity was determined using DPPH (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging model. Five concentrations of extracts prepared in methanol having a final DPPH radical concentration of 0.1mM. The mixture was shaken vigorously for 1min then left to stand for 60 min in the dark. Scavenging capacity was measured spectrophotometrically at 518 nm. Ascorbic acid was used as a positive control. Methanol served as the blank. Inhibition (%) was plotted against the sample concentration in the reaction system. The percentage inhibition of the DPPH radical calculated according to the following formula:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = [(A \text{ control} - A \text{ sample}) / A \text{ control}] \times 100$$

Where A is absorbance.

Superoxide radical scavenging activity:

The assay tubes contained 0.02ml of the leaves and stems extracts (corresponding to 20mg extract) with 0.2ml EDTA, 0.1 ml nitroblue tetrazolium, 0.05ml riboflavin and 2.64ml phosphate buffer. The control tubes were set up without the leaf extracts, where DMSO was added. The initial optical densities of the solutions were recorded at 560nm and the tubes were illuminated uniformly with the fluorescent lamp for 30 minutes. A₅₆₀ was measured again and the difference in O.D was taken as the quantum of superoxide production (20). The percentage inhibition by the leaf samples was calculated by comparing with the O.D of the control tubes.

Nitric oxide radical scavenging activity:

Nitric Oxide scavenging activity was measured spectrophotometrically (Banerjee *et al.*, 2011). Extracts were added to different test tubes in different concentrations. Sodium nitroprusside in phosphate buffer was added to each test tube. Solutions were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes. Thereafter, 1.5 ml of Griess reagent was added to each test tube. The absorbance of the chromophore formed, indicative of the quantum of NO generated, was read at 546 nm and percentage of scavenging activity was measured with reference to ascorbic acid as standard.

Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity:

The hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of the leaves and stems extracts was quantified by the method reported by Elizabeth and Rao (1990). The reaction mixture (0.1 ml) contained 0.1 ml of deoxyribose, 0.1 ml of FeCl₃, 0.1 ml of EDTA, 0.1 ml of H₂O₂, 0.1 ml of ascorbate, 0.1 ml of KH₂PO₄-KOH buffer and 20 µl of leaf extracts (20 mg) in a final volume of 1.0 ml. The reaction mixture was incubated for 1 hour at 37°C. Then 1.0 ml of TBA was added and heated in a boiling water bath for 20 minutes. The pink colour produced was measured at 535 nm in a spectrophotometer. Deoxyribose degradation was measured as TBARS and the per cent inhibition was calculated.

Antimicrobial activity:**Inoculum preparation:**

Fresh microbial cultures were prepared by streaking loopful of bacterial suspension into organism specific selective media (Himedia) and incubated at optimal temperature in order to maintain approximately uniform growth rate of each organism. The bacterial cultures from fresh media were compared with 0.5 McFarland turbidity standards, which is equivalent to approximately 1 x 10⁸ bacterial cell counts per ml (21, 22), were maintained throughout the experimentation.

Well Diffusion Method

Antimicrobial properties of leaves and stems extracts with the help of agar well diffusion method. Luria Bertane agar plates were prepared for leaves and stems extracts. Inoculum (50 µl) of each selected bacterium (gram positive bacteria like *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* and gram negative bacteria namely, *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli*) was uniformly spreaded on agar plates with the help of glass spreader, after five minutes, wells were bored. The equal volume of antibiotic (Tetramycin), distilled water and extracts (n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and aqueous extracts of leaves and stems) were individually poured into the wells. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After 24 h of incubation the zone of inhibition was investigated (Amit *et al.* 2011). Undiluted overnight broth cultures should never be used as an Inoculum routine direct application of suitably diluted extracts are poured into the well. Sterile water was used as control. (23). Then, approximately 20 µl of each extract (1 mg/ml) and antibiotic tetramycin (20 µg/ml) was separately introduced into wells and allowed to diffuse at room temperature. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs and then examined for clear zones of inhibition. After incubation, the diameter of inhibition zone was measured by ruler and recorded in millimeters (24).

Antifungal Activity -Disc Diffusion Assays:

In vitro antifungal screening was performed by disc diffusion assay method (Bear *et al.*, 1966; Rios *et al.*, 1988). The n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br and ethyl acetate fractions were tested against two fungi (*Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*) at a concentrations of 20 µg/disc, 50 µg/disc and 100 µg/disc for each and the results were compared with fungal (200 µg/disc). The activity was determined after 72 hours of incubation at 37.5°C. The fungal strains were collected from pathology laboratory, Department of energy science department, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai.

Antibiofilm activity**Sample collection and isolation of pure cultures:**

Pseudomonas aeruginosa MTCC 2543 and *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 1430 were collected from MTCC Pune.

Microtitre plate assay:

The overnight grown cultures were diluted to 1:100 in Nutrient broth medium with 1% glucose. From this 100 µl of medium was added to each of five wells of microtitre plate and incubated for 48 h at 30°C. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* was removed and the wells were washed with sterile distilled water. 125 µl of crystal violet solution was added to each well and incubated for 10 min at room temperature. Excess stain was removed by washing with sterile water. The plate was inverted over paper towel and tapped vigorously to remove excess of liquid if any and allowed to dry. 200 µl of 95% alcohol was added to each well and allowed the dye to solubilize by incubating for 15 min at room temperature. The contents of each well were then briefly mixed by pipetting and then observed for optical density readings 25.

Antiangiogenic assay- Chorioallantoic Membrane Assay (CAM)

Fertile white Leghorn chicken eggs (*Gallus domesticus*) were obtained from a local hatchery with 6 days incubation. The eggs will be incubated at 37°C in humidified incubator for 48 h, placed in horizontal position and rotated several times. The eggs were grouped as per type of extracts and sprayed with 70% ethanol and air-dried to reduce contamination from the egg surface. On 6th day fertilized egg was punctured a small hole in the air sac of the egg, with 26-gauge needle and 2-3 mL of albumen will sucked and

sealed. This allows separation of vascularized CAM from the vitelline membrane and the shell. A window was then cut in the shell using a sterile blade and shell will be removed with sterile forceps, under laminar air flow. The window is closed with a cellophane tape after capturing the photographs of the embryo. The eggs are returned to the incubator after the filter paper discs (100 micro litters of extract) of the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) *R.Br* extracts are placed on blood vessels of embryo using sterile forceps. After 48 h of incubation on 8th day photographs of embryos are taken to obtain the image of CAM after treatment with various extracts. At least six eggs are used for each extract dose. The percentage inhibition is calculated using the following equation 26.

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{\text{No .of vessels in untreated} - \text{No. of vessels in treated}}{\text{No .of vessels in untreated}} \times 100$$

Ovicidal and Larvicidal assay:

Collection of eggs and maintenance of larvae

Egg hatching and larval development - Eggs of *Anopheles stephensi*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus* were collected from the National Centre for Disease Control field station of Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India, using an "O"-type brush and were reared in insectariums of the department at 25 – 28°C temperature. The eggs, deposited on paper strips were submerged into tap or distilled water and allowed to develop until reach the larval stage. Mosquito ova and larvae were provided the food as per standard protocols. These eggs were brought to the laboratory and transferred to 18×13×4-cm enamel trays containing 500 mL of water for hatching. The mosquito larvae were fed with pedigree dog biscuits and yeast at 3:1 ratio. The feeding was continued until the larvae transformed into the pupal stage.

Ovicidal assay:

Effect of the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) *R.Br* extracts on the hatchability of *Anopheles stephensi*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus* eggs were determined and hatching rate was calculated on the basis of non-hatchability of eggs. Five replications were conducted at each extracts concentration (%). Egg hatching rate was monitored for 24h. The assays were developed at 25°C. Of continuous exposure and this was expressed as percent mortality.

Larvicidal assay:

The assay was performed by exposing twenty (I, II, III and IV instar) larvae of *Anopheles stephensi*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus*. Concentration of plant extracts (%) were used. The water temperature maintained at 25± 1°C. For each test three beakers containing distilled water and test larvae but without sample were used as controls. Observation on mortality and deformities of the larvae was recorded after every 24 hrs. Larvicidal rate was monitored for 24h. The assays were developed at 25°C. Of continuous exposure and this was expressed as percent mortality of the test larvae were killed.

The control was set up by mixing 1 mL of acetone with 249 mL of dechlorinated water. The ova and larvae were exposed to dechlorinated water without acetone served as control. The control mortalities were corrected by using Abbott's (1925) formula.

$$\text{Corrected mortality} = \frac{\text{Observed mortality in treatment} - \text{Observed mortality in control}}{100 - \text{Control mortality}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Percentage mortality} = \frac{\text{Number of dead ova/ larvae}}{\text{Number of ova/ larvae introduced}} \times 100$$

Anticancer Assays:

Cell lines:

Hep-2(human epithelial larynx cancer cell line) was obtained from the National Centre for Cell Sciences, Pune, India. The cells were grown in MEM medium supplemented with 10% FBS and antibiotic solution. The cells were maintained in T-25 tissue culture flasks at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere in 5% CO₂ incubator. Exponentially growing cells were used in all the experiments.

Cell counting:

10 µl of cell suspension was added to 10 µl trypan blue dye (0.4%) and mixed well. After 1-2 minutes, 10 µl of the mixture was loaded onto a clean haemocytometer and observed under the bright field microscope under a 10X objective with a total magnification of 100X.

Cytotoxicity assay - MTT assay:

Cells were seeded in a 96 well plate. Cells were exposed to the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) *R.Br* extracts for different time periods. MTT dye (0.5 mg/ml) was added 4 hours

prior to completion of incubation period into each well. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was carefully taken out and the resulting formazan crystals were solubilized by adding 200 µl of DMSO. The absorbance was measured at 595 nm.

$$\text{Cell proliferation inhibition (\%)} = (1 - \text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} / \text{OD}_{\text{Control}}) \times 100$$

$$\text{Viable cells\%} = (\text{OD of drug-treated sample} / \text{OD of untreated sample}) \times 100$$

Statistical analyses

All the experiments were done in three replicates and the results were expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation (SD).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study was carried out to determine the bioactive efficiency in *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R Br leaves and stems. In an effort to understand the nature of the active principles in the leaves and stems, they were serially extracted into organic solvents of increasing polarity (n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and distilled water) by soxhlet method.

Further n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and distilled water of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R Br leaves and stems phytochemical and antioxidant analysis was carried out to identify the bioactive constituent present in the leaves and stems of this plant and then *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R Br leaves and stem extracts were evaluated for their efficiency against different pathogenic bacteria and fungi under in-vitro conditions.

Phytochemical studies:

From the qualitative analysis of leaves and stem extracts of selected medicinal plant *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn) R Br, the presence or absence of carbohydrates, proteins, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, glycosides, triterpenoids, tannins, sterol, saponins, phytosterol and diterpenes were investigated. The results of this study are shown in the Table 2 and Figure 1.

Table: 2 Preliminary phytochemical investigation of *C. gigantea* (L.) R. Br leaves and stems.

Phytoconstituents analysis in the different organic plant extracts of <i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) R.Br leaves and stems								
Phytochemical Compounds	Organic Solvent Extracts of plant							
	Leaves				Stems			
	H	EA	E	A	H	EA	E	A
1 Alkaloids								
a) Dragendroff's test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
b) Mayer's test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
c) Wagner's test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
d) Hager's test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2 Glycosides								
a) Baljet's Test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
b) Keller-Killiani test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
3 Proteins								
a) Ninhydrin test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
b) Biuret test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
c) Xanthoprotein test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4 Carbohydrates								
a) Molisch's test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
b) Fehling's test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5 Tannins								
a) Lead Sub Acetate	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
b) Ferric Chloride Test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
6 Saponins								
a) Foam test	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
7 Flavonoids								
a) Ammonium Test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
b) Aluminium Chloride Test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
8 Steroids								
a) Liebermann-Burchard test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
9 Terpenoids								
a) Salkowski Test	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

(+) indicate the presence of phytoconstituents, (-) indicate the absence of phytoconstituents.

Preliminary phytochemical identification tests A) Liebermann-Burchard test B) Salkowski test was performed as per standard procedure (16-18) which revealed that the presence of steroids and terpenoids compounds in *C. gigantea* (Linn) R Br leaves and stems extracts.

Thin Layer chromatography (TLC) screening

A small portion of the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems were dissolved in respective solvents and the solutions were spotted on TLC plates. Then the TLC plates were run by specific solvent system and viewed individually under UV light and Liebermann-Burchard reagent (Harborne, 1973 & 1984, Kumar et al 2007) was used as spray. Different colored spots on TLC plate indicated the presence of different type of compound in each extracts. Pink or red colouration spots indicated terpenoids, violet to blue colouration spots indicated steroids.

The result of qualitative analysis showed that phytochemicals especially steroids and terpenoids were present in the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude leaves and stems extracts of *C. gigantea* (Linn) R Br studied.

Figure 1 shows steroids and terpenoids phytochemical analysis of *C. gigantea* (Linn) R Br leaves and stems extracts A) Liebermann-Burchard test B) Salkowski test (right). Steroids and terpenoids identification test (Liebermann-Burchard reagent) on TLC plate (left).

Note: C- control, R- reagent, H- n-heptane extract, EA- ethyl acetate extract, E- ethanol extract, A- aqueous extract.

In vitro antioxidant studies:

The result of the antioxidant studies are shown in Figure 2 A to E. antioxidant activity (A) DPPH radical scavenging activity- i. Dot-blot method, ii. DPPH photometric assay, B) Superoxide radical scavenging activity, C) Nitric oxide radical scavenging activity, D) Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity) of *Calotropis gigantea* is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 shows the antioxidant activity A) DPPH radical scavenging activity- i. Dot-blot method, ii. DPPH photometric assay, B) Superoxide radical scavenging activity, C) Nitric oxide radical scavenging activity, D) Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity.

The dot-blot test is an easy, fast and reliable way to compare radical scavenging capacity. This assay was used to establish whether different extracts of *Calotropis gigantea* (L.) R. Br leaves and stem (n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and aqueous) had radical scavenging activity. When DPPH reacts with a hydrogen donor, the reduced (molecular) form (DPPH) is generated, accompanied by the disappearance of the violet colour (16, 19).

The dot plot assay is shown in Figure 2 A (i). In this assay, the maximum DPPH scavenging activity was expressed by the ethyl acetate extract, ethanolic extract followed by the aqueous extract of *C. gigantea* (L.) R. Br leaves and stem. Considerable scavenging effects were also noted with the other extracts. Respective concentrations of *C. gigantea* extracts as well as standard compound (Ascorbic acid) were accepted and the volume was constituted uniformly using methanol. Each of the samples was then promote diluted with methanol and to each DPPH was added. Absorbance was taken after 30 min reaction period at room temperature in dark place 518nm using methanol as blank (20). DPPH is used to evaluate the free radical scavenging activity (antioxidant potential) of the medicinal plants. (28, 29).

DPPH is stable free radicals potentially reactive with substance able to donate a hydrogen atom and thus useful to asses compounds antioxidant activity of specific compounds f extracts 30. Because of its odd electron, DPPH has a strong absorption band at 517 nm. The observed percentage of inhibition are shown in Figure 2 A(ii) Since this electron becomes paired in the presence of a free radical scavenger, the absorption decreases stoichiometrically with respect to the number of electrons taken up. This change in absorbance produced by this reaction has been widely used to test the ability of several molecules to act as free radical scavengers (31). In Figure 2 B shows the superoxide radical scavenging assay showed that the ethyl acetate extracts seem to be potent active when compared to the other solvents. Figure 2 C shows the nitric oxide radical scavenging assay of ethyl acetate extracts of leaves and stems was efficient when compared to the other solvents. Figure 2 D shows the hydroxyl radical scavenging effect was analysed to be high in the ethyl acetate extract of leaves and stems.

Antimicrobial activity:

In the present study to screen *C. gigantea* plant leaves and stems extracts against certain gram positive bacteria (*B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*) and gram negative bacteria (*aeruginosa* and *E. coli*) were used. The antibacterial activity was studied by agar well diffusion method. Antibacterial activity of different solvent extract of *Calotropis gigantea* is shown in Table 3 that the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and aqueous extracts of leaves and stem of *C. gigantea* impart sufficient inhibitory actions against the test microbe ranging from 6 mm to 25 mm diameter inhibitory zones. And out of these n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and aqueous extracts, limited inhibition was observe in ethyl acetate and aqueous extracts in leaves and ethyl acetate and aqueous extracts in stem. Antifungal activity of the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *C. gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br by disc Diffusion Assays and extracts were tested against two fungi (*Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*) at a concentrations of 20 µg/disc and the results were showed in Table 3. 50 µg/disc and 100 µg/disc for each extracts of leaves and stems and the results were showed in graph.

Table: 3 Antibacterial investigation by Agar well diffusion method.

Antibacterial Activity of <i>C.gigantea</i> (L.) R. Br leaves & stems extracts										
S. no	Pathogenic bacteria	Conc µg/ml	Zone of Inhibition (mm)							
			<i>C.gigantea</i> (L) R. Br leaves extracts				<i>C.gigantea</i> (L) R. Br stems extracts			
			HE	EAE	EE	AE	HE	EAE	EE	AE
A	<i>B. subtilis</i>	20	5±2	22±2	3±1	13±1	6±2	23±2	7±4	11±2
	Antibiotic (20µg/ml)		20±1	20±1	20±1	20±1	20±1	20±1	20±1	20±1
B	<i>S. aureus</i>	20	3±2	25±2	5±4	11±1	7±5	24±2	11±2	10±1
	Antibiotic (20µg/ml)		21±1	21±1	21±1	21±1	21±1	21±1	21±1	21±1
C	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	20	5±4	21±2	3±1	11±1	7±3	22±2	6±1	5±4
	Antibiotic (20µg/ml)		17±1	17±1	17±1	17±1	17±1	17±1	17±1	17±1
D	<i>E. coli</i>	20	3±2	19±1	5±2	15±2	5±2	19±2	11±3	7±2
	Antibiotic (20µg/ml)		15±1	15±1	15±1	15±1	15±1	15±1	15±1	15±1
+ ve Control = Sterile water			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Antibacterial activity of different solvent extracts of *C. gigantea* showed varying degrees of antibacterial activity against all microorganisms tested. (32) There are many reports of plants in the family *Asclepiadaceae* possessing anti-microbial activity. (33, 34) From this study it can be said that, ethyl acetate extracts of *C. gigantea* leaves and stems showed wide range of antibacterial activity can be used and administered in the ethno medical practice. The results obtained from our study showed an effective inhibition against the test organisms which justify the traditional use of the plant *C. gigantea* leaves and stems for infection diseases.

Figure: 3 shows antifungal investigation by Disc diffusion method.

The ethyl acetate fraction showed best antifungal activity against all the tested fungi. It might be due to the presence of high concentration of active phytochemicals in ethyl acetate extract or due to presence of these phytochemicals in ethyl acetate fraction. The results of antifungal activity (zone of inhibition) of test materials against respective fungi were given in the Figure 3. Any chemical substance or biological agent that destroys or suppresses the growth of microorganism is called antimicrobial agent. Antimicrobial screening of a crude extract or pure compound isolated from natural sources is essential to ascertain its activity against various types of pathogenic organisms. Earlier studies proved the strong antimicrobial effect of the root extract of *Calotropis gigantea* against pathogenic bacteria. Some other studies reflect *Calotropis gigantea* as a potent source of variety of medicinal compounds 35.

Antibiofilm activity

Biofilms plays a crucial role in the emergence of new pathogens by horizontal transfer of genetic elements. Hence there is a critical need for the identification of antibiofilm compounds with potential application against these pathogens. The inhibitory activities of the extracts live up to their potential in the treatment of microbially-induced ailments or diseased conditions, in line with the traditional use of plant extracts. The initial mode of microbial life is biofilm and they can be harmful to both human life and industrial processes. Hence, development of efficient biofilm control strategies is of the utmost importance due their direct impact on public health and the economy. In human medicine, it has been estimated that 65% of nosocomial infections are biofilm associated, costing the health care system billions of dollar. The antibiotics available for the treatment of biofilm-related infections is minimal 36. High, moderate and no growth of biofilm effects were showed in Figure 4.

Figure 4 shows the antibiofilm effect of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* against various extracts of *C. gigantea* leaves and stems.

Mosquitocidal Activity

Ovicidal and Larvicidal assay:

Effect of the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br extracts on the hatchability of *Anopheles stephensi*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus* eggs were determined and hatching rate were expressed in Figure 5. Effect of the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br extracts on the hatchability of *Anopheles stephensi*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus* larval stages (I-IV) were determined and mortality rate were expressed in graph. In conclusion, the present work is a preliminary study for the screening of mosquito ovicidal and larvicidal activity in which high mortality rate exposed in ethyl acetate and water followed by ethanol crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br. The presented report indicates mosquito controlling potential of *C. gigantea* Figure 5. In future these plants can be used as an alternative source for the development of new mosquito controlling agents. Further studies can be made to investigate the active principle of the insecticidal compound present in the tested plants.

Figure 5 shows Ovicidal and Larvicidal activity of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br leaves and stems with *Anopheles stephensi*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus*.

Antiangiogenic - Chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) assays

Chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) assays have been greatly used to study angiogenesis, metastasis and tumour cell invasion (37). Hertig first named the word angiogenesis in 1935, and Folkman revealed the mechanism in studying tumour angiogenesis (38). The CAM assay has become an extensively used tool for the determination of angiogenesis property and anti-angiogenic property of various drugs including herbal extracts. The accomplishment of anti-angiogenic therapy for treating cancer has led to an explosion in the field of research for potential anti-angiogenic agents (39).

Effect of different extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br on the angiogenesis of chick chorioallantoic membrane (CAM). A 0.5 cm-diameter filter paper loaded with or without extracts were applied to the CAM and incubated at 37°C for 72 h. Angiogenesis around the filter was counted. The number of blood vessels was quantified manually in a circular perimeter surrounding the implants, at a distance of 0.25 cm from the edge of the filter. Assays were performed twice. Quantification of CAM assay and percentage of inhibition represented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Antiangiogenic effect of Chick Egg Chorioallantoic Membrane Assay (CAM).

In vitro Cytotoxicity -MTT assay:

The percent viability was analyzed by MTT assay after treatment with different extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br extracts showed in the figure. The results obtained for the cell survival as determined by MTT assay, The cytotoxic assays have been carried out in order to assess the optimal concentration at which, the ethyl acetate extracts of leaves and stems gives maximum protection to the cells. Cytotoxic assays MTT were used to analyze the cytotoxic effects of the n-heptane, ethyl acetate, ethanol and water crude extracts of leaves and stems of *Calotropis gigantea* (Linn.) R.Br extracts in Hep-2 cells. Over all extracts, the ethyl acetate extracts of leaves and stems showed maximum percentage of inhibition which is expressed as graph in figure 7.

Figure 7 Cytotoxicity effects represented by MTT assay.

CONCLUSION

The present study indicates that the presence of steroids and terpenoids compounds and exudate of *Calotropis gigantea* has got intense antimicrobial, antioxidant, antibiofilm, antiangiogenic and cytotoxic activity and may have potential use in medicine. From the previous studies and our current investigation showed potential values on ethyl acetate extract of stems and leaves. It may be concluded that further study can be carried out to investigate the individual bioactive principles. We conclude that *C. gigantea* represents an unexplored source of potentially useful compounds and it worth for future clinical use. In addition, urgent measures have to be taken to preserve the traditional knowledge about medicinal plants.

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